

Biomimetic microgels for articular cartilage regeneration. A minipig knee model.

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to explore, with an *in vivo* model, the regeneration of articular cartilage that can be obtained with a strategy that combines the stimulation of the subchondral bone with the implantation of a biomimetic microgel at the site of the cartilage defect. The microgel consists of an agglomerate of two types of microspheres: ones rigid, made of a biodegradable polyester, and the other ones composed of a polymeric network of gelatin and hyaluronic acid that encapsulate platelet-rich plasma (PRP) obtained from circulating autologous blood. A defect of 7 mm in diameter and full depth was performed in the articular cartilage at the trochlea of the animal knee, using a minipig model. Microdrilling was performed in the underlying bone and the defect was filled with the microgel in which the platelets it contains were previously activated with calcium chloride. The whole defect containing the microgel was covered with a synthetic membrane to avoid the release of microspheres. The results of the *in vivo* follow-up of the experiment, the histological analysis and the mechanical measurements of the regenerated tissue 9 months after implantation were compared with those of a group of animals in which only microdrilling was performed and the defect was covered with the membrane and with another group in which a clinical use commercial collagen mesh was implanted. The mean value of the elastic modulus of the newly formed tissue was not significantly different from that of the native tissue in the case of microgel implantation while its content of GAGs, was significantly better than in the other groups.

Keywords: cartilage engineering, *in vivo*, microgel, platelets rich plasma, hyaline, gelatin, hyaluronic acid.

1. Introduction

The clinical application of tissue engineering techniques for articular cartilage regeneration dates back to the 1990s with the first generation of autologous chondrocyte transplantation (ACI)[1]. In this technique, chondrocytes are obtained from a biopsy of the patient's articular cartilage, from a healthy, unloaded area. These chondrocytes are expanded in culture, and it is known to produce a change in their phenotype which called dedifferentiation, which results in the production of type I collagen in very significant quantities, instead of the type II collagen that is characteristic of articular hyaline cartilage, as well as a defect in the production of glycosaminoglycans (GAGs). By reimplanting these cells at the defect site and covering it with a sheet of inverted periosteum extracted from the tibia, or with a biological or synthetic membrane, it is expected that these chondrocytes will recover the original phenotype and can produce tissue with the histological characteristics and mechanical properties of the native hyaline cartilage, but this occurs only partially and the newly formed tissue degenerates over time [2–5]. Another possible source of cells to regenerate the defect are mesenchymal stem cells, MSCs. MSCs from bone marrow (and from other sources) have demonstrated their ability to differentiate into chondrocytes both *in vivo* and *in vitro* if they find the appropriate microenvironment and receive the necessary biomechanical and biochemical signals [6–8].

The different techniques used in the clinic injure the subchondral bone in different ways, producing bleeding at the defect site (the so-called bone marrow stimulation techniques), and the fibrin clot formed acts as a pathway for the migration of MSCs from subchondral bone [9].

When microfracture, microdrilling or other stimulation techniques of the subchondral bone are used, the generation of a tissue with cartilage characteristics is observed, but closer to fibrocartilage than to hyaline cartilage, and without the mechanical properties required for it to be functional [10,11]. Other approaches use different cells with chondrogenic capacity that are isolated from different tissues, expanded, and transplanted to the site of the cartilage defect with or without prior *in vitro* differentiation in a chondrogenic medium [7].

Both cases demonstrate the need to add a supporting biomaterial so that chondrogenic cells find an environment that provides protection, initial anchorage points and a biomechanical environment similar to the natural one, when they arrive or are transplanted to the defect site. The joint is subjected to high dynamic compressive loads. In native hyaline cartilage, chondrocytes are isolated in lacunae that protect them from excessive loading but transmit mechanical stresses that mediate gene transcription through a pathway called mechanotransduction [12,13]. Thus, as in other tissues of the musculoskeletal system, mechanical stress on the tissue is essential for maintaining the phenotype of its cells.

A large number of support structures (scaffolds, hydrogels) and countless biomaterials have been investigated for cartilage regeneration [7,14,15]. In particular, the use of hydrogels has recently become more widespread thanks to advances in bioprinting, in addition to their ability to encapsulate cells in environments containing the key biomolecules of the natural microenvironment [16–18]. In a previous work, we demonstrated the potential of microgels in the regeneration of this tissue in an experimental model of articular cartilage injury in rabbit knee [19]. We refer to the agglomeration of microspheres in a liquid medium as microgels. These microspheres can have the consistency of a gel themselves, but they can also be more rigid. In both cases, when the cells occupy the space between the microspheres, they find an environment somewhat analogous to that found when they are encapsulated in a hydrogel, but with the difference that the microspheres can move so that the cells acquire the capacity to migrate, or to accumulate the extracellular matrix they produce. This facility is essential in the case of articular cartilage regeneration because the biomaterial is an impediment for the newly formed tissue to organize itself, by forming columns of round cells encapsulated in lacunae in the medial or deep zone, perpendicular to the articular surface, and to differentiate it from the superficial zone with cells that are flatter and parallel to the surface.

Microgels can be biomimetic if the microspheres that form them are coated with components of the extracellular matrix or with biomolecules that recapitulate the composition of the tissue. It is also possible to get the microspheres to release drugs or growth factors [19,20]. In reference [19] we used a microgel formed by a mixture of chitosan microspheres and polylactic acid, PLA, microspheres. We obtained quite promising results, since we observed the formation of a neotissue with the histological characteristics of hyaline cartilage, well integrated into the edges, and also the particles

of the implanted biomaterial had completely disappeared from the regenerated tissue, either because the time the implant was maintained was sufficient for its bioresorption, or in the case of PLA because the newly formed tissue displaced the microspheres towards the subchondral bone. However, certain anomalous effects appeared that were attributed to the presence of chitosan [19]. It is known that the results obtained in the rabbit model are not always reproduced in higher animals or in patients. The ease of regeneration of this animal makes the results of this model overestimate the regenerative capacity of the strategy tested.

The purpose of the current investigation is to explore the regeneration obtained by combining microdrilling of the subchondral bone with the implantation of a microgel at the site of damage in a porcine knee model and compared with more simple approaches. The new microgel consists of a combination of PLA with a mixture of microspheres made of gelatin and hyaluronic acid containing platelet-rich plasma, PRP, obtained from autologous circulating blood, as a source of growth factors that can enhance cell migration. PRP has already been used in cartilage regeneration studies [21–23] and has also been applied in the clinic for the treatment of osteoarthritis [24–26], with controversial results.

The biocompatibility of gelatin microspheres containing PRP has been studied by in vitro assays showing the biocompatibility of this environment and the role of PRP in the expression of miRNAs related to chondrogenesis [23]. Moreover, in vitro studies have demonstrated the viability of mesenchymal stem cells encapsulated in gelatin hydrogels and tyraminated hyaluronic acid. [27,28]

We hypothesize this combined approach (microdrilling + augmentation with microsphere and PRP) would be more effective for cartilage regeneration than microdrilling alone or combined with a collagen mesh.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

Type A gelatine from porcine skin (G2500-100G), hyaluronic acid sodium salt from *Streptococcus equi* (53747), 2-(N-morpholino)ethanesulfonic acid (M3671-50G), N-hydroxysuccinimide (130672-25G), tyramine hydrochloride (T2879-25G), hydrogen peroxide solution 30 % (w/w) in H₂O, containing stabilizer (H1009-500 ml), type VI horseradish peroxidase, essentially salt-free, lyophilized powder, ≥ 250 units/mg solid

(P8375-1KU), olive oil tested according to Pharmacopoeia Europaea (75343-1L), calcium chloride dihydrate (C8106-500G), sodium chloride ReagentPlus®, ≥99% (S9625-5KG), poly(vinyl alcohol) average Mw 130,000, 99+% hydrolyzed (563900-500g) and 12000 molecular weight cut-off dialysis tubing cellulose membrane (D9652-100FT) were purchased from Sigma. Other reagents are Dulbecco's phosphate buffered saline (DPBS) from Gibco (14200-059). Medical grade poly-lactic acid (PLA) (Purasorb PL-18) from Corbion, N-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-N'-ethylcarbodiimide (RL-1022.0250) from Iris Biotech. Liquid soy lecithin (Mg97588) from Guinama. Chloroform, EssentQ®, stabilized with ethanol (CL02002500) from Scharlab. Spectra/Por® 3 Dialysis Membranes, MWCO 3500 (VWR 25219-085) purchased to VWR. The clinical collagen mesh was purchased by A2C Suministros Hospitalarios, Spain.

2.2. Microgel production

PLA microspheres

PLA microspheres were fabricated by dropping a 2% w/v PLA solution in chloroform into a 4% w/v poly(vinyl alcohol) solution using an oil/water emulsion method. Briefly, 20 mL of PLA solution (oil phase) was filtered (0.45 µm nylon filter) and pumped at 1 mL/min into 200 mL of PVA solution under constant stirring at 750 rpm to generate the oil/water emulsion. Then 150 mL of deionized water was added and stirring was maintained during 24 h. The microparticle suspension was washed twice with water and once with ethanol, before being sieved through a 70 µm mesh. The plasma treatment was performed with a Piccolo (Plasma Electronic) Microwave plasma chamber. The plasma treatment parameters were Argon gas, 50 Pa initial gas pressure, with a gas flow rate of 160 standard cm²/min, sccm, during 600 s, at 360 W of potence and a separation of 8 cm from the source. The microparticles were stored in Eppendorf tubes and sterilized with gamma rays at a dose of 25 kGys (Aragogamma). FESEM images were obtained with FSEM ZEIS ULTRA 55 and particle diameter distribution was determined with ImageJ software.

PLA electrospun membrane

PLA was dissolved at 10% w/v in a chloroform/acetone (70/30 v/v) mixture, filtered with a 45 µm nylon filter, and loaded into a syringe with a 0.5 mm inner diameter needle. The

polymer solution was pumped at a rate of 8 mL/h with a distance of 15 cm to the collector for 30 min at 20 kV voltage. The sample was washed 4 times with ethanol and dried under vacuum. Membrane hydrophilicity was improved with plasma treatment. Plasma treatment, FESEM imaging, and sterilization were performed as described above for PLA microspheres. The diameter of the fibrils was determined with ImageJ software. Membrane thickness was determined with MiniTest 3100 device from ElektroPhysik

Tyramine derivatives of Gelatin and Hyaluronic acid (HA)

Tyramine substitution was performed through the reaction of carbodiimide with carboxyl groups of gelatin, following previous works [27]. The gelatin was dissolved at 2% w/v in 20 mL of ultrapure water with 0.98% w/v of MES at 60 °C and 0.56% w/v of tyramine, before equilibrating the solution to pH 6. The crosslinking reagents (0.04% w/v NHS and 0.61% w/v EDC) were added, and the sample was incubated at 37 °C with shaking to allow the reaction. The sample was purified by dialysis against ultrapure water. The molecular weight of the original HA was reduced by acidic degradation following the procedure by Shu *et al.* [24]. The low molecular weight HA was dissolved at 0.5% w/v in 20 mL of ultrapure water with 0.88% w/v of NaCl and 5.40% w/v MES at room temperature at pH 5.75. Once dissolved, 0.87% w/v tyramine was added, before correcting the pH of the solution to pH 5.75. The crosslinking reagents (0.01% w/v NHS and 0.16% w/v EDC) were added and once dissolved, the sample was incubated at 37 °C with shaking to allow the reaction. The sample was poured onto a cellulose membrane to dialyze and remove small molecules, changing the wash with NaCl 0.88% w/v every 8 h for 24 h and finally with ultrapure water for 2 days. Finally, tyramined polymers were sterilized by filtration (0.22 µm filter) and lyophilized under sterile conditions. The degree of tyramine substitution was determined from the absorbance at 275 nm (Perkin Elmer 1420 Multilabel counter Victor3) and is expressed as a percentage of the tyramine groups relative to the original carboxyl groups in the polymer.

Preparation of microspheres

GEL/HA/PRP microspheres were obtained using microfluidics by mixing tyramined gelatine (tGel), tyramined hyaluronic acid (tHA) and PRP. PRP was obtained under sterile conditions from the blood of each animal, collected 1 to 2 h before surgery. Blood was collected into 5 mL citrate vacuum tubes and gently mixed to prevent blood clotting.

Blood was centrifuged for 18 min at 1800 rpm. One quarter of the plasma volume was collected from the part of the tube next to the red fraction, which is considered as PRP, and the rest of the plasma was discarded. The PRP was stored at 4 °C until use.

Poly(dimethyl siloxane), PDMS, microfluidic systems were home-made as described in [30] and sterilized (sketch is shown in figure 1a) with gamma rays at a dose of 25 kGys (Aragogamma), in a laminar flow cabin close to the surgery room to avoid contamination. A solution of tHA 3% (w/v) and tGel 3% (w/v) dissolved in calcium-free Krebs-Ringer buffer (115 mM NaCl, 5 mM KCl, 1 mM KH₂PO₄ and 25 mM HEPES at pH 7.4), was mixed with PRP and 12.5 U/mL and HRP in a 4:4:1 ratio. This solution was pumped through the insertion point C (Figure 1a) as a discontinuous phase at 2 mL/h. Olive oil with 2% of soy lecithin (sterilized at 150 °C for 90 min) was pumped through insertion point B as a continuous oil phase at 30 mL/h. Finally, a microemulsion of sterile H₂O₂ in olive oil (8 mL H₂O₂ with 32 mL olive oil with 2% of soy lecithin) homogenized by sonication was pumped through insertion point A (Figure 1a) at 10 mL/h. Briefly, the continuous phase cuts the stream of polymer solution into small droplets that coagulate when the H₂O₂ activates the enzyme. The obtained microspheres were incubated at room temperature within the oil for 10 min to complete the crosslinking reaction before removing the oil by filtration. A custom-made collecting tube was performed by inserting a 60 µm mesh sieve into a 50 ml tube. The samples were centrifuged at 500 rpm for 3 min, which allowed the oil to be separated from the microgel. The microspheres were then washed with DPBS, removing any remaining oil in the supernatant. Finally, the GEL/HA/PRP microspheres were mixed at 50/50 v/v with the PLA microspheres and incubated in presence of CaCl₂ 0.5% w/v in a sterile tube and immediately transplanted to the cartilage defect performed in the animal. As a control for material characterization, microspheres prepared with the same protocol but without PRP were produced, which will be named GEL/HA microspheres.

Figure 1. (a) Schema of the microfluidic circuit. The H_2O_2 -in-oil emulsion stream enters the system through inlet A, the continuous medium stream through inlet B, and the aqueous solution of tGEL, tHA, PRP, and HRP enzyme through inlet C. (b) Optical microscope images of the GEL/HA/PRP microspheres. (c) Size distribution of the microspheres that were implanted in the animal model. (d) FESEM microscopy of PLA microspheres.

2.3. Animal model. Surgery

The animal model was performed at the Jesús Usón Minimally Invasive Surgery Centre (JUMISC, Cáceres, Spain), which belongs to the NANBIOSIS Singular Scientific and Technological Infrastructures Platform, Spain. The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Comunidad de Extremadura, Spain.

In this study, twelve 14-months-old minipigs (Specific Pig SL, Spain) were used, which included 6 males and 6 females. The joint was approached with a 5 cm medial parapatellar incision. Once the joint was exposed a chondral defect was performed on the medial facet of the trochlear groove of the minipig stifle joint, as previously reported [31]. A circular full-thickness defect in the articular cartilage was made using a 7-mm diameter disposable biopsy punch (KAI Medical, Seki, Japan). The articular cartilage was meticulously debrided down to the subchondral bone using a surgical bone curette. Special care was taken to ensure that the edges of the defect were clean and well defined. The microdrillings of the underlying bone were then performed using a 0.8-mm diameter drill. Three perforations were done in each defect (Figure 2a). The applied treatment was different depending on the allocated group (Table 1).

The animals were randomly divided in three groups: group D corresponds to the negative control in which the microdrillings of the subchondral bone were performed as described above, covered with the microporous electrospun PLA membrane, but without implanting any biomaterial filling the lesion. In group C, the microdrillings were performed and a commercial clinical collagen mesh, the same size as the defect made, was implanted in the defect. And finally, in group M the microdrillings were combined with the implantation of a 50/50% v/v mixture of PLA and PRP microspheres filling the lesion (Figure 2b), covered with the microporous electrospun PLA membrane (Figure 2c). Autologous microspheres were produced for each animal from an extraction of its own blood and platelets were activated immediately before the intervention.

This study was designed according with the 3Rs using both knees of 12 animals, reducing the number of study animals by half, as detailed in Table 1. The animals received antibiotics and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, NSAIDs, for one week after the procedure, as postoperative treatment. Gait analysis of the animals with Tekscan Walkway® system was performed 3 times during the experiment, and computed tomography (CT) images were recorded at the same time points to assess the preservation of the subchondral plate.

Table 1. Distribution of the experimental series in the animals.

1 st animal		2 nd animal		3 rd animal		4 th animal	
Left knee	Right knee	Left knee	Right knee	Left knee	Right knee	Left knee	Right knee
Group D	Group C	Group C	Group M	Group M	Group D	Group C	Group D
5 th animal		6 th animal		7 th animal		8 th animal	
Left knee	Right knee	Left knee	Right knee	Left knee	Right knee	Left knee	Right knee
Group M	Group C	Group D	Group M	Group D	Group C	Group C	Group M
9 th animal		10 th animal		11 th animal		12 th animal	
Left knee	Right knee	Left knee	Right knee	Left knee	Right knee	Left knee	Right knee
Group M	Group D	Group C	Group D	Group M	Group C	Group D	Group M

2.4. Histological analysis

The animals were sacrificed nine months after surgery, by an overdose of thiopental, and the knees were isolated and examined macroscopically following the ICRS score [32]. These samples were collected from the trochlear region and then cut frontally into two

halves. One half is used for mechanical testing, and the other half for histological testing. The area not affected by the surgical intervention is used as a native control (Figure 2). To prepare the samples for the microscopic study, the knees were fixed in 4% formalin and subsequently immersed in a decalcifying solution (Osteosoft®, Merck Life Science S.L.U, Madrid, Spain). Four months later, the knees were ready to be histologically processed. Samples were embedded in paraffin and 5-7 µm sections were obtained using a standard manual rotatory microtome (Leica, Madrid, Spain). For microscopic measurements, haematoxylin-eosin (HE) and toluidine blue (TB) stains, and polarized light microscopy were used. In each knee, the defect area was identified and the cartilage adjacent to the defect was used as a native control. The following morphological parameters were analysed in the injured area: cartilage thickness, cell density, interdigitating index, and TB-stained positive area (GAGs area). All measurements were carried out by two independent observers and k coefficients [33] were calculated to establish the consistency of observations. Statistical analysis included a Kolmogorov-Smirnov test to determine the normal distribution of the data and ANOVA for comparison of means. Significant differences were established below $p < 0.05$.

2.5. Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of the regenerated tissue were assessed using a Seiko TMA/6000 device in compression mode, employing a 1 mm diameter stainless steel probe. Samples were selected to include cartilage and a segment of knee bone, featuring a prismatic geometry with approximate dimensions of 10×10×5 mm.

Figure 2. Images of the surgical approach. (a) Cartilage defect in the trochlear groove of the femoral condyle in which microdrillings have been performed. (b) The cartilage defect filled with the microgel. (c) The defect filled with the microgel and covered with the electrospun PLA membrane. (d) The site of regeneration 9 months after surgery showing sampling for mechanical and histological analysis. The black line represents the explanted area of the animal. The red line represents the frontal(?) division of the sample: the upper half is used for mechanical testing, and the lower half for histological studies. The green dots represent the areas used to indent the regenerated cartilage, and the blue ones for the healthy cartilage.

A load ramp was applied at a constant rate of 10 g/min. Then an unloading ramp followed at the same rate, and the sample was allowed to recover with no applied loading for 10 min. This process was repeated 3-5 times per sample. Experiments were conducted at 37 °C in a saline solution. Stress-strain curves from the loading phase were constructed using the experimental data, and a linear fit of the initial 10% of the curve was used to determine Young's modulus for all cartilage samples. The slope of this line correlates with Young's modulus (E) according to the equation:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\varepsilon} = \frac{2\kappa E}{\pi a(1 - \nu^2)} t \quad (1)$$

where σ is the applied stress, a is the probe radius, ν is the Poisson's ratio, t is the cartilage thickness, ε is the sample strain, and κ is a correction factor that takes into account the effect of finite layer, which depends on ν and the a/t ratio [34]. The κ values can be found in Table 1 of reference [35]

Sample thickness was measured from cross-sections observed under an optical microscope. The sample strain was then calculated as the displacement divided by the cartilage thickness. Since the Poisson ratio could not be directly measured, a value of $\nu = 0.4$ was assumed to compute E from the indentation tests [36,37]. This assumption is not highly restrictive here, since E is relatively insensitive to minor variations in ν . Considering that the surrounding bone is significantly more rigid than the cartilage, it was also assumed that all deformation occurred in the cartilage layer, with bone deformation being negligible in this procedure.

To analyse significant differences in the elastic modulus calculation, a Fisher test was performed to determine whether the variances of the samples were equal or different. Then, the t-test was performed, assuming equal or unequal variances, as appropriate.

3. Results

3.1. Microgels

The purpose of the GEL/HA/PRP microspheres is twofold: on the one hand, to encapsulate PRP without or only partially activating the platelets. On the other hand, the mixture of tGEL and tHA combines the protein with cell adhesion sequences and the polysaccharide with high water absorption capacity, mimicking the composition of articular cartilage [28].

Platelets are known to release about 90% of platelet growth factors abruptly, within the first hour after activation [38]. Since the microsphere manufacturing procedure requires washes in aqueous medium, any factors released before these washes are likely to be lost before the microgel is transplanted to the cartilage defect site. Therefore, in the procedure employed in this work, the microdroplets formed in the microfluidic circuit coagulate by crosslinking of gelatin and hyaluronic acid chains modified with tyramine groups. In a previous work we have shown that crosslinking tGEL mixed with PRP only partially activates platelets and they maintain their capacity to release factors after activation with a calcium chloride solution [23].

In tGel, 24.1% of the carboxyl groups were substituted by tyramine and in tHA the substitution ratio was around 3.7%. These results were in the order of those reported in previous studies [27,39]. Crosslinking takes place when the HRP enzyme, contained in the polymer solution, is activated by hydrogen peroxide which is introduced in the circuit in the form of an oil dispersion once the microdroplets have been formed.

The circuit operating parameters were selected looking for the stability of the system and the average size of microspheres in the range of 150 μm , which had been used in previous works in animal models or in cell culture [19,23]. The design of the microfluidic system took into account the effect of the angle at which the channels cross on the hydrodynamics of the system. Thus, in the formation of the microdroplets at point B (Figure 1a) the angle of crossing is greater than 90° to increase the pressure in the zone, while in the mixing of the continuous medium with the H_2O_2 emulsion at point C for the coagulation of the droplets, an angle of less than 90° is used to facilitate the homogeneous mixing of the two flows with less pressure on the channel walls, thus avoiding the appearance of turbulence and the deformation of the droplets. With a flow rate of 30 mL/h of continuous medium, 2 mL/h of discontinuous medium and 10 mL/h of H_2O_2 emulsion, a bead diameter of $155.7 \pm 33.7 \mu\text{m}$ was obtained. An image of the microspheres obtained with optical microscopy is shown in figure 1b, while the size distribution is shown in figure 1c.

On the other hand, the PLA microspheres obtained by oil-in-water emulsion had an average diameter of $46.7 \pm 15.7 \mu\text{m}$, three times smaller than the GEL/HA/PRP particles. A representative FESEM image is shown in figure 1d. The difference in size between both types of particles favours their packing at the implant site. The huge dispersion showed in the size of PLA particle is characteristic of the emulsion procedure used to produce them. Finally, the electrospun PLA membrane obtained had a thickness of $68.0 \pm 8.9 \mu\text{m}$ and showed a porous structure formed by fibres with a diameter of $1,6 \pm 0,7 \mu\text{m}$.

3.2. *In vivo* assessment throughout the study

Our study aims to validate the hypothesis that articular hyaline cartilage formation can be generated at the site of a cartilage defect by combining microdrilling of the subchondral bone plate that opens a pathway for chondrogenic cells to reach the site of damage and filling the chondral defect with a microgel that provides these cells with a biomimetic environment while the mobility of the microspheres that form it allows the organization of the neo-formed tissue. In this regard, we compared a series of animals treated with our strategy, series M: microgel + microdrilling + membrane covering the defect, with a series of animals in which only the microdrilling was performed and the defect was covered with the membrane, series D. Differences between the biological response in these two series would give us information about the role of the biomaterial in regeneration. We are

also interested in looking for differences in the response when the implanted biomaterial is a microgel compared to the implantation of a more conventional scaffold, such as a collagen fibres mesh (series C).

One of the relevant problems in the repair of articular cartilage and even more so in the repair of osteochondral defects, is the maintenance of the integrity of the subchondral plate. It has been observed in rabbit knee models that, although the subchondral bone is significantly damaged, the subchondral plate regenerates and it has even been observed that when a relatively rigid scaffold was implanted in the cartilage area, the dynamic compression loads have sunk it in the bone and yet the subchondral plate has reattached to the implant. This is perhaps one of the differentiating facts between the animal model in rabbits and in higher animals, where new cartilage formation often occurs but the articular surface is not smooth because the subchondral plate has collapsed [40,41]. In this work we performed computed tomography (CT) scans throughout the experiment at three times, 3, 6 and 9 months, before the sacrifice of the animals, trying to see if this effect occurs (results not shown). However, in the present study we verified the integrity of the subchondral plate by CT, in all animals and in all series. Also, in the histological studies performed on the samples, it is observed that the subchondral plate has not been affected by regeneration (Figure 3).

The animals' gait was also monitored throughout the trial using the Tekscan Walkway® system, to determine whether the animal protected one of its hind legs while walking as an indication of knee pain. Differences were found in some animals between the gait of the two hind legs at early moments, with no correlation found between the knee that caused pain and the intervention performed on that knee. Over time, these differences in gait tended to disappear and were attributed more to wound healing from the surgery than to cartilage injury.

Figure 3. Images showing the characteristics of the regenerated tissue in a case in which regeneration is considered positive. (a) Macroscopic image of the articular surface. (b) Cross section showing that the thickness of the regenerated cartilage is similar to the original cartilage, and the subchondral plate has been preserved. (c) Complete section of the joint stained with haematoxylin-eosin showing that the newly formed tissue homogeneously fills the defect originated in the cartilage. (d) Complete section of the joint stained with toluidine blue showing the glycosaminoglycans content in the newly formed tissue. Arrows indicate the site of regenerated tissue. Bars in (a) and (b) correspond to 7mm and in (c) and (d) to 500 μm .

3.3. Histological evaluation

Figure 3a shows the macroscopic image of the articular surface in the area of regeneration, in a case of positive regeneration. Both the macroscopic cross-sectional image (Figure 3b) and the histological sections showing HE (Figure 3c) and TB (Figure 3d) stains of sections of the entire femoral condyle, show the integrity of the subchondral plate, a complete filling of the defect and a relatively smooth articular surface. These aspects are applicable to all animals in the series in which the defect was filled with a biomaterial, either the microgel of the M series or the collagen membrane of the C series. However, the quality of the newly formed tissue presented a great variability, especially regarding the amount of GAGs present in the tissue, as we describe in detail in the following paragraphs.

The native articular cartilage showed an ordered histological organization, consisting of chondrocytes surrounded by a hyaline GAG-rich matrix with a characteristic distribution of type II collagen fibres, determining the characteristic zones of this tissue, which are the superficial zone with flattened cells and fibres parallel to the surface, the intermediate zone and, in contact with the subchondral plate, the deep zone characterized by

chondrocytes organized in radial isogenic groups, with thicker collagen fibres between them, both perpendicular to the surface (Figure 4, column A). This tissue showed a thickness of $624.8 \pm 100.7 \mu\text{m}$, with a cell density of $52.94 \pm 8.87 \text{ cells/mm}^2$ and an interdigitating index of 1.019.

In the microdrilling group, the defect was partially filled by a neotissue consisting, in general, of a fibrotic repair tissue with evident cellular disorganization and a replacement of the characteristic hyaline cartilaginous matrix by a fibrocartilage like matrix, poor in GAG and with the presence, in some cases, neovascularization and white adipocytes. The cells contained in that matrix acquired a fibroblastic morphology and were not organized into isogenic groups. Likewise, polarized light microscopy showed a complete loss in the characteristic organization of healthy articular cartilage tissue (Figure 4, column B). The thickness of this newly formed repair tissue was lower than that of native cartilage ($430.4 \pm 145.2 \mu\text{m}$) and the cell density was significantly higher (104.2 ± 52.02).

In the knees in which microdrilling was complemented with another treatment (collagen mesh or microgel) we observed great variability in the animals studied. In some samples the defect was filled with a hyaline-like neotissue in terms of thickness, cell distribution, fibrillary organization as well as GAG content, as can be observed with TB staining (Figure 4, column C). In these animals, abundant isogenic groups of cells with chondroblastic morphology were observed, surrounded by a hyaline matrix with the characteristic territorial areas. However, in other animals the synthesized neotissue presented characteristics of fibrocartilage, with a disorganized matrix with a fibrous appearance, poorer in GAG, and abundant elongated cells (Figure 4, column D). The 42.86% of the animals in the collagen mesh group showed good regeneration with a thickness of the newly formed cartilage of $586.7 \pm 170.5 \mu\text{m}$ and a cell density of $92.29 \pm 14.25 \text{ cells/mm}^2$. In the microgel group, 66.67% of the animals showed a good regeneration, with a thickness of $525.6 \pm 95.4 \mu\text{m}$ and a cell density of $75.88 \pm 6.96 \text{ cells/mm}^2$.

Macroscopic evaluation of cartilage repair according to the ICRS score did not show significant differences in relation to treatment (Table 2). In the three experimental groups analysed, the newly formed tissue in the defect area was significantly thinner than in the native cartilage, although no significant differences were found between the treated groups (Figure 5A). However, the histological characteristics of the newly formed matrix presented differences in relation to the GAG-rich area, revealed by TB staining. In native cartilage, all cartilage stained positively with TB stain (Figure 5E). The matrix enriched

in GAGs begins to form in the area of contact with the subchondral plate and progresses towards the most superficial areas of the articular cartilage, where a more fibrotic tissue is observed. The TB-stained area was larger in the microdrilling+microgel group (Figure 5H) compared to microdrilling alone (Figure 5F), or to microdrilling+collagen mesh (Figure 5G). In all the samples studied, the regeneration pattern was similar. The cells in contact with subchondral bone showed a rounded morphology very similar to that characteristic of chondrocytes and were surrounded by a GAG-rich matrix. We also observed groups of cells that appeared to be "chondrification centres" where not only there were a significant amount of GAGs, but also collagen fibres appeared ordered and provided a hyaline-like appearance, similar to that of native cartilage. After measuring the positive area for TB staining, we found that it was significantly higher in animals in which microdrilling was combined with microgel treatment, as summarized in Figure 5B. We also measured the cell density of the newly formed tissue. As shown in Figure 5C, in all experimental groups included in this study, a higher cell density was observed in the injured area compared to the native uninjured area. However, these differences did not reach statistical significance. Regarding the interdigitation index, no differences were found between groups (Figure 5D).

Figure 4. Histological images obtained with polarized light (pol. light) microscopy and with haematoxylin-eosin (HE) or toluidine blue (TB) stainings. Column A shows images of the native tissue. Column B shows images of an animal from series D, in which only microdrillings were performed. Column C corresponds to an example of positive regeneration in an animal in which the biomaterial was implanted. Column D corresponds to a case of a medium-poor regeneration, also with biomaterial that filled the defect (see text). Bars correspond to 100 μm (pol. light C, D, HE 20x, and TB 20x), 200 μm (pol. light A, B) or 500 μm (HE 5x, TB 5x).

Figure 5. Characteristics of the newly formed tissue at the site of injury. (A) Thickness of articular cartilage in the regeneration area. (B) Area occupied by GAG-rich tissue. (C) Cell density. (D) Interdigitation Index. (E) TB staining of native cartilage. (F, G, H) Details of TB-stained histological sections of animal samples from series D (only microdrilling), C (microdrilling+collagen mesh, and M (microdrilling+microgel) respectively. The image selected in each case was the one that presented an area stained with TB with the value closest to the mean value of its series. Bars correspond to 100 μm .

It is known that the composition of articular cartilage is responsible for its mechanical properties. Healthy hyaline cartilage contains between 70 and 75% of water, while the

GAGs content can be up to 20% depending on the joints, and areas of cartilage with type II collagen can represent between 11 and 20% wet weight. A deficit in GAGs leads to a tissue with poorer mechanical properties, such as fibrocartilage, and the action of mechanical stresses can cause its degeneration. Figure 6a shows the result of an indentation test on a regenerated tissue with high GAG content as shown in figure 3, compared with that of healthy tissue (Figure 6b).

The figures show the loading and strain profile as a function of time in three consecutive loading ramps with the unloading ramps in between. The stress/penetration profile at the first indentation ramp is shown in figure 6c. After the first loading ramp, the test shows that in the unloading ramp the tissue is not able to recover the deformation in step with the decrease of the applied load and in fact the indenter detaches from the specimen at the point marked with the white arrow.

On the next loading ramp, the indenter also takes time to make contact with the sample, as marked by the black arrow. The difference in strain between these two points indicates that during the resting time in which the sample is kept without any load, the tissue has continued to recover from the indentation. The behavior of a sample poorer in GAGs, as that shown in figure 5G is shown in figure 6d, compared to native tissue from the same animal (Figure 6e). In this case, it can be seen that the initial slope of the stress/penetration curve is representative of a lower elastic modulus than in the previous case, corresponding to a softer tissue.

Figure 6. Stress-strain curves in indentation tests (a) representative sample of a high GAG content, as that shown in Figure 3. Figure (b) shows the result in the native tissue of the same animal and (c) the stress-strain curve from which the elastic modulus has been calculated. Curve (d) corresponds to a sample with poorer GAGs content, as that shown in Figure 5G, compared to its native tissue (e). Curve (f) shows how it is a softer regenerated tissue.

The elastic modulus values were calculated from the slope of the stress-strain figures in the first 10% strain, according to equation (1). Figure 7 shows the average values found in each of the series. While both series D and C show significantly lower values than in the native tissue, in the case of the series in which the microgel was implanted, series M, there were no significant differences although the average value of the modulus is also somewhat lower than that of the native tissue. On the other hand, there were no statistically significant differences between the M series and the D or C series. Tissue recoverability was also evaluated as the difference in penetration between the point at which the loading ramp begins and the point at which the indenter detaches from the sample in the unloading ramp, but no significant differences were found between the three groups studied or between each group and the native healthy tissue.

Figure 7. Elastic modulus for the three groups studied, and for the native healthy tissue. No significant differences were found between group D, C, and M, nor between group M and healthy tissue, but there were differences between the native healthy tissue and groups D and C ($*p < 0.05$).

4. Discussion

Modifying the gelatin and hyaluronic acid chains to graft tyramine groups onto them consumes a relatively small portion of the carboxyl groups present in the chains.

Crosslinking with HRP forms a single network since crosslinking points can form either between chains of the same component or between a point on a tGEL chain and a point on a tHA chain. The enzymatic crosslinking occurs between phenol groups of tyramine and is therefore useful for encapsulating cells or platelets without affecting their viability and functionality. The rate at which the reaction occurs is compatible with the processes in the microfluidic channel. The aqueous solution of tGEL, tHA and HRP is stable and can be injected into the circuit without danger of clogging the channels. The microdroplets are formed at the first junction with the continuous medium and remain liquid until they come into contact with the hydrogen peroxide at the second cross where then gelification takes place in few seconds and when they leave the circuit, they have sufficient consistency not to agglomerate. The PRP is retained, and the platelets are only activated a moment before being implanted at the injury site. At that moment, the platelets release thrombin, which causes the plasma to clot forming an interpenetrated network where the platelets are encapsulated releasing their growth factors. The entire process, starting with tGEL and tHA, takes about one hour, which is compatible with the preparation for surgery. The consistency of the microspheres is that of a gel and when mixed with PLA microspheres with a minimum of saline medium they form a paste with which the surgeon can fill the cartilage defect. To prevent the biomaterial from detaching, it is covered with the electrospun PLA membrane.

The blood that flows from the holes drilled in the subchondral bone impregnates the microgel and penetrates by capillary action into the micropores of the membrane and, after coagulation, fixes it without the need for sutures or surgical glues. The fibrin clot produced by the blood agglomerates the microparticles of the microgel and acts as a migration pathway for the pluripotent cells that invade the site of damage from the subchondral bone. The microspheres function as a scaffold on whose surfaces the cells find adhesion points on the protein chains that form the GEL/HA/PRP microspheres and on the other hand, the microgel transmits to the cells the mechanical stresses derived from the dynamic compression to which the joint is subjected. Furthermore, cells can interact with the HA of the microspheres through the CD44 cell membrane receptor that has been described to be chondrogenic [28].

Many of the different tissue engineering approaches for the manufacture of scaffolds capable of inducing chondral regeneration are based on experiments performed *in vitro*. These models are valid for the study of factors related to the control of cellular differentiation, factors related to genes or epigenetic control systems related to

differentiation into chondrocytes, their proliferation, the effect of physical factors or pharmacological screening. However, nowadays, mimicking the biophysiological events which occur during articular cartilage and bone healing *in vivo* is virtually impossible. Therefore, suitable animal models are needed for critical evaluation and assessment of the expected clinical impact of any new treatment protocol [42].

On the other hand, choosing the animal experimental model is not easy, given that there is no model equivalent to what happens in humans. There are factors, including the weight of the animals, joint loading, cartilage dimensions such as thickness and organization, among others, which influence the interpretation and translation of experimental data [43].

Small animals, such as rabbits or rats, have been widely used in the literature, but exhibit a great capacity for endogenous regeneration, making them good models for a proof of concept, but not good models for translation to the clinic [44]. Larger animals include the sheep, goat, or dog. Since the first two are ruminants, they exhibit complications related to housing and surgical facilities due to the risks of transmission of prion diseases [45]. The articular cartilage of dogs shares the same collagen arrangement as humans, however, as they are pets, their use is more complex from an ethical point of view. The minipig constitutes a good alternative for a large animal model since, although the thickness of the articular cartilage is smaller than that of humans (0.5-0.8 mm), it has a similar histological organization. It is also a docile animal with a stable weight between 30-50 kg that is maintained in adults, and with biochemical parameters in blood and a liver enzyme profile equal that of humans [46].

Gotterbarm *et al.* studied a total of 46 chondral defects in minipigs and found that the critical defect size was 5 mm. They studied the animals at 6, 12 and 52 weeks after surgery, observing that the defect was completely filled with fibrocartilage that initially exhibited metachromasia, but subsequently lost this property, leaving its surface disrupted [42].

One of the objectives of this work was to evaluate whether the use of a microgel generated with PRP from the patient could improve the reference techniques currently used in trauma practice. For this reason, in the present study we used microdrilling combined or not with the collagen mesh or with our microgel to fill in defects. We used a time point of nine months, which is long enough to rule out any endogenous regeneration in this model. We have found different degrees of regeneration in the defects studied. Regarding microdrilling, we generally observed worse regeneration compared to knees in which a

complementary treatment was used. However, the newly formed tissue exhibited greater integrity and thickness than previously published data in which only the defect was performed [42].

Treatment supplemented with a collagen mesh provided some improvement over simple microdrilling. In some animals, the newly formed tissue showed characteristics of hyalin cartilage. However, in others the results were not so good. This variability in the use of a collagen mesh has been reported by other authors. Peras *et al.* published a multicenter retrospective study of 101 patients, 2 years after being treated with AMIC for knee osteochondral defects. They concluded that AMIC significantly improved patients' functional and radiological scores, but this procedure seemed to produce similar outcomes to those obtained using other available techniques [47]. Thus, we cannot conclude whether the data obtained in this experimental group are due to the variability of the treatment itself or to the low number of animals used, which constitutes one of the weaknesses of our study. In this regard, we have followed the 3R rule to reduce the animals used as much as possible and, although we lack the statistical power necessary to establish further conclusions, the data obtained are promising and reinforce the need to carry out new studies to support the conclusions of this study.

Regarding microgel-treated defects, the results obtained in all the parameters analysed are as good as in the case of the collagen mesh. Furthermore, we have found a significant difference in the synthesis of GAGs, finding a greater area rich in GAGs in this group compared to the other two experimental groups. In this regard, we have found that the synthesis of GAGs begins in the area adjacent to the subchondral plate and progresses towards the surface, so that the regeneration of the matrix appears to occur from the depth of the cartilage towards the surface. Moreover, the cells in this area had a rounded morphology very similar to the characteristic of chondrocytes, and cells were surrounded by a matrix rich in GAGs. We also observed clusters of cells that appeared to be "chondrification centres" where not only were there a significant amount of GAGs, but also collagen fibres appeared ordered and provided a hyaline-like aspect similar to that of native cartilage. Polarized light microscopy data seem to indicate that the accumulation of GAGs precedes the organization of collagen fibres that provide the structural support of articular cartilage and is related to the appearance of isogenic groups of chondrocyte-like cells. The role of the subchondral plate in the maintenance of articular cartilage is well known, in fact, it is considered an osteochondral complex [48]. At the base of the subchondral plate there is a venous plexus responsible for supplying nutrients and

biochemical factors to the base of the articular cartilage. Thus, there are diffusion experiments of sodium fluorescein that demonstrate the existence of channels that allow this diffusion [49]. In this way, some techniques such as drilling seek to increase this permeability. Collagen scaffolds could generate mechanical support that, together with the increased permeability of the microdrilling, would explain the benefits of its use. In our case, we have combined this support with a release system of factors included in the PRP. There is evidence that PRP not only induces the expression of anti-inflammatory molecules and represses the expression of pro-inflammatory ones, but also regulates the perfusion of substances through the subchondral plate, favouring the regeneration and preservation of articular cartilage [50–52].

The mean values of the elastic modulus correlate with the histological assessments of the regenerated tissue. Histologically, it is observed that when regeneration is imperfect, the tissue zone richest in GAGs is located next to the bone, while the superficial area is more similar to fibrocartilage. In some of the samples, after nine months of regeneration, the layer close to the articular surface is deficient in GAGs and, as a consequence, this tissue is softer than the native tissue. In all three series of samples there are animals with more or less complete regeneration in the sense that the thickness of this softer tissue layer is more or less thick. The results of the indentation tests (Figure 7) show that while in group M the mean value of the elastic modulus is not statistically different from that of the native tissue, both groups D and C showed on average a lower stiffness than the native tissue. Thus, the values of the elastic modulus correlate with the area of GAG-rich tissue shown in Figure 5b.

A limitation of our study is that it is not possible to draw conclusions about the role played by each of the microgel components in regeneration (gelatine, hyaluronic acid, PRP, PLA microspheres), since the need to reduce the number of animals used in the model as much as possible makes it impossible to prepare experimental series for this purpose.

5. Conclusions

Microspheres that simulate the composition of cartilage tissue have been produced by microfluidics. They consist of an enzymatically cross-linked network of gelatin and hyaluronic acid capable of retaining autologous platelet-rich plasma. Upon subsequent platelet activation, an interpenetrating network is formed that encapsulates platelets

releasing growth factors that can activate tissue regeneration. These hydrogel-like microspheres have been combined with other stiffer microspheres to form a microgel that has been tested to promote articular cartilage regeneration in an in vivo model. The results obtained with the microgel implantation in a minipig animal model have shown great variability, with several cases of very positive regeneration in which the neo-formed tissue shows the histological characteristics of hyaline cartilage, rich in GAGs, with a good cellular organization, preserving the subchondral plate and with mechanical properties that do not differ significantly from native cartilage. In other animals of the same group, although a layer of tissue rich in GAGs is formed next to the bone, its thickness does not cover the entire thickness of the tissue formed, having on the surface a tissue more similar to fibrocartilage. However, the quality of the regenerated tissue in this group of animals is, in this aspect, significantly better than in the group in which a collagen mesh was implanted or in which only microdrilling was performed and the defect was covered with the membrane. On the other hand, the mean value of the elastic modulus of the tissue is not significantly different from that of the native tissue in the case of microgel implantation, while it is significantly lower in the other two groups.

Acknowledgements

The animal model was conducted at the Jesús Usón Minimally Invasive Surgery Centre (JUMISC), Spain. The assistance in the surgical procedures of Francisco Javier Vela, Elena Abellán and Laura Cristina Pires Louça is greatly acknowledged. The authors also thank the microscopy department of the Universitat Politècnica de València for their help and support. This work was supported by the projects PDC2021-121658-C21 and -C22, funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by the European Union “NextGenerationEU”/PRTR. The research was also supported by CIBER-Consortio Centro de Investigación Biomédica en Red – CB06/01/1026, Instituto de Salud Carlos III, Ministry of Science and Innovation.

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